

Factors For The Development Of Keative Qualities Of Teachers Of Military Education Up To The Upcoming Call

Jalilov N.A.

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after
Nizami Faculty of Military Education Methodological
training cycle P.f.f.d (PhD)

Abstract: *In this article, a good idea and reasoning is analyzed about the factors of developing the creative qualities of future teachers of military education and the main factors of teaching students.*

Keywords — science, creative, creative, creative, divergent, education, enlightenment, intellectual, intelligence, euretistic.

INTRODUCTION.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.In Mirziyoyev's "strategy of New Uzbekistan", the greatest wealth is intelligence and science, the greatest inheritance is good upbringing, the greatest poverty is ignorance! Therefore, for all of us, mastering advanced knowledge, becoming truly enlightened and the owner of a high culture should become a continuous vital need [1]- it is important that they think. The main goal is to transform the youth into a person of wide-ranging content thinking and intellectual potential in the views expressed by our president.

Also, the psychologist Scientist E.Geziyev summarized psychological factors in scientific psychology with a large volume of materials, laws, features, thoughtful conclusions are drawn that have a universal description of a person's inner potential, talent, performance, ability. This results in the possibility of identifying, predicting the psyche of a person, being free from existing mental defects, preventing negative experiences, which serves to rationally characterize the essence of Social, Social Psychological bonds [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]- he emphasizes.

A.R.Aripdzhanova, on the other hand, environmental factors affect the individual, the development of his creative and creative qualities, in turn, the process of creation is determined by the specifics of both the problem and the individual. It defines the characteristics of this product that the individual seeks [3]-states the idea.

In Particular, V.N.Drucin [3], J.Guilford [4], E.R.Based on his analysis of the works of Torrance [5]s, "he has shed light on a number of personal factors for the development of creative qualities.

Ye.A.Shmeleva identified abilities and personal characteristics that affect the formation and development of creativity [6]; "divergence of thinking; specificity of thinking; semantic flexibility; ability to identify and Arise a problem; ability to generate many ideas; ability to analyze; ability to

overcome stereotypes; ability to find many associations" [7]- he notes.

D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya believes that stimulation is an effective or passive level. Representatives of this level of intellectual activity work energetically and conscientiously, but initially remain within the framework of the found method of action. Their activities are without initiative. It is stimulated from the outside every time [8]- expresses the idea that.

Euretistic degree. It is characterized by the manifestation of one or another intellectual initiative of future teachers with this level of intellectual activity, which is not stimulated by external factors or subjectively evaluates the results of activities as unsatisfactory.[12]

Ye.A.Shmeleva notes that the owner of the development of such intellectual activity is able to analyze the composition and structure of his activities, compare tasks, and this leads to the discovery of new specific ways of solving [6].

D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya is recognized as the most important factor in creativity and is identified in many sensitivity tests. Such a future teacher will try to penetrate into the depths of the problem, although he will not be forced to do it by Hecht kim. He leads the object of knowledge to the creation of a theory that explains the essence of facts and tries to understand the causes of phenomena, their own. Thus, the psychological barrier that prevents future teachers from getting out of a certain situation is eliminated. In this case, there is no need to compare a number of situations, and you can limit yourself to solving only one problem, but for this, the thoughtful opinion that it is necessary to find evidence of the phenomenon [8] is also relevant.

Also, a distinctive feature of each representative is his approach to the task. Thus, a person with a stimulating – productive level increases the pace of work in a certain framework and mechanically reproduces his activities on an expanded scale, applies more and more new methods of solving the heuristic problem, and the creative person delves deeper into the topic, finding theoretical explanations for the phenomenon[8]-emphasizes.

In particular, the psychologist Scientist E.R.Torrance identifies several factors that positively influence the development of creative qualities of prospective teachers. Giving constructive information, developing constructive criticism, not criticism, encouraging self-esteem, eliminating the fear of assessment[5]- showed that.

It is the recognition of the value of creative thinking, the development of the sensitivity of prospective teachers to environmental stimuli, the free manipulation of objects and ideas about the creative process [6**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]- gave that permission.

E.R.Torrance emphasizes sensitivity to problems and understanding them as a factor of creativity, and describes their knowledge, ability to seek solutions, assumptions, dissatisfaction with the formation of hypotheses, as well as creativity from the point of view of thinking J.R.Guilford agrees [9**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

J.R.Creative thinking, according to Guilford, is the process of feeling difficulty, problems, gaps in information, missing elements, bias in something, predicting shortcomings and forming hypotheses, the possibility of evaluating and examining these assumptions and hypotheses, revising and checking them, and, finally, generalizing and achieving results [4]-claims to be.

Fig-1. Factors affecting the development of creative qualities of future military education trainees

A.Maslow states that the development of creative qualities is influenced by the personal characteristics of students, as well as emotional and motivational factors. At the same time, there is currently no consensus on the motivational properties of creativity in pedagogy and psychology. According to some researchers, creative qualities try to make an individual understand himself in the best possible way, to match his capabilities as much as possible, to master new types of activities. It is believed that the “stimulation of creative qualities of future teachers is based on testing the limits of their

capabilities”[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]- the same is the opinion.

I.A.Alyoxin stimulation is the external influence on the individual, the community, the group of people, as well as on the personal composition, the activation of their motivational sphere and, through it, a certain activity [11**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]- it is appropriate to say.

According to the analysis of scientific affairs, the future conscription of teachers of educational education to stimulate the activities of the development of creative qualities – to the future conscription, the influence on the personality of teachers of military education through external factors, their motivational action, activation and development are considered.[12]

Ye.A.Shmeleva believes that the general scientific, pedagogical-psychological basis of the development of the personality of future teachers is the elimination of social problems on the basis of adaptation to social emotions, the priority of a socialized environment as a factor characterizing the educational process, attitude to society and organization of theoretical approaches and social pedagogical ideas on the development of [6].

From this point of view, the following factors affecting the acquisition of cognitive knowledge and the development of creative qualities of teachers of military education up to the future call in the process of creative thinking are distinguished by their positive effect. It is formed under the influence of the personality of any person, society, family. It is society, its existing educational system, traditions and traditions that form the most important personality qualities in a person.[13]

These qualities are characteristic of most people, but they are manifested individually, depending on the specific circumstances, environment, upbringing. It is impossible to deny the existence of a genetic predisposition of different people to the formation of certain personal characteristics.[14]

Thus, the factors that influence the development of creative qualities of future teachers are of two types: situational and personal element.[15]

Situational factors that negatively affect a person's creative qualities include: time limit; stress state; increased anxiety State; High desire to quickly find a solution;[16] too strong or too weak motivation; having a firm mind for a particular solution; self-doubt due to previous failures; fear; untenability of determination; tasks that trigger the wrong way of solving conditions [17]

Personality factors are stable traits, personality traits, or personality traits that can affect conditions caused by a particular situation.[18]

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